

Commentary

Eosinophils have a critical role in promoting pancreatic malignancy in experimental chronic pancreatitis

Dr. Lokanatha Orauganti, PhD
SRF in DST-SERB Project
Dept. of Biochem, SVU, Tirupati.
Email: oruganti.loka@gmail.com

(Received Feb 12, 2022; Accepted Mar 20, 2022)

Purpose of Study.

Kandikattu, and Manohar recently published in Life Science Alliance 2021 that Macrophage derived NLRP3 regulated IL-18 induced eosinophilia promote chronic pancreatitis associated pancreatic malignancy.

Study Population.

Eight- to 10-week-old BALB/c mice, interleukin, GATA-1 gene-targeted mice, and IL-18-deficient inbred mice are used to establish eosinophil's role in promoting malignancy in chronic pancreatitis.

Methods.

Using previously published protocols, mice were treated with cerulein and azoximethane by repeated intravenous 3 injection/week for 16 weeks.

Eosinophils accumulation and degranulation in the pancreas was analyzed along with the development of malignant phenotype in the pancreas. The tissue distribution of eosinophils and its association with the development of pancreatic malignant characteristics were examined in the tissue sections of saline, cerulein and ceulein with azoxymethane treated mice. Pathologic and molecular changes using histologic, PCR, ELISA and immunoblot analysis

Reviewer's Comments.

Eosinophils are a type of leukocytes that respond to various allergic stimuli and play an important role in allergic illness. The role of Eosinophils has been implicated in pancreatitis and pancreatic cancer development too. Several clinical findings have shown that excessive eosinophil infiltration occurs in pancreatic biopsies resulting in

eosinophilic pancreatitis (EP) which mimic pancreatic neoplasia, and it is also observed that eosinophils are commonly found in pancreatic tumors. EP is not a rare disease, rather it is an underappreciated or unstudied condition. As a result, understanding the mechanism of eosinophil accumulation during pancreatitis and pancreatic fibrosis, including malignancy, is critical to throw light on eosinophilic pancreatitis (EP) (Manohar et al., 2021).

To determine the involvement of eosinophils in human pancreatitis, researchers looked at eosinophils in the pancreas of healthy people and pancreatitis patients. Eosinophils make up about 0-4 percent of total WBC cells. It was observed that eosinophil buildup occurs in human pancreatitis, despite the absence of eosinophils in the pancreatic tissue section of a healthy person (Manohar et al., 2018). To understand the molecular mechanisms of eosinophils involved chronic pancreatitis and pancreatitis cancer, cerulein-induced murine model as well as cerulein-AOM-induced murine models were developed and experiments were conducted.

Increased tissue eosinophilia, as well as mast cell and acinar cell atrophy were observed in a cerulein-induced murine model of chronic pancreatitis. Increased mRNA and protein levels of proinflammatory and profibrotic cytokines and chemokines such as IL 5, IL-18, eotaxin-1, eotaxin-2, TGF- β 1, collagen-1, collagen-3, fibronectin, and α -SMA were identified using qPCR and ELISAs.

Whereas, the eosinophil-deficient GATA1 and endogenous IL-5-deficient cerulein-induced mouse model of pancreatitis were protected from the production of proinflammatory and profibrotic cytokines, chemokines, tissue eosinophilia, and mast cells (Manohar et al., 2018).

Eosinophilic extracellular MBP granules in pancreatitis tissue have shown crucial impacts on mast cells and acinar cells releasing histamines and digesting enzymes respectively. MBP produced from eosinophils has the ability to activate and degranulate mast cells (Niranjan et Al., 2013). It was shown that reduced acinar cell damage, inflammatory cell infiltration, collagen production, and mast cell accumulation were found in cerulean induced IL-5 gene-deficient mice and eosinophil-deficient GATA1 mice (Manohar et al., 2021). RT-PCR and ELISA data showed a significant rise in mRNA and protein levels of IL-18, eotaxin-1, eotaxin-2, and IL-5 indicating their role in increasing eosinophil accumulation and degranulation during pancreatitis development in cerulin induced mice when compared to normal control mice.

EP is often confused with PC due to similar clinical symptoms, and certain cases of PC are accompanied with eosinophilia (Euscher et al, 2000). Eosinophils produce the profibrotic cytokine TGF- β which is important in promoting pancreatic fibrosis via the signalling protein SMAD4, which may lead to the development of

the typical characteristics seen in PC (Kandikattu et al, 2021a).

The cerulein-induced mouse model of pancreatitis is well-established, however the presence of eosinophils is seldom investigated (Xue et al., 2015). AOM, a gene mutation agent, has previously been utilised in laboratory animals to produce inflammation-mediated cancer features (Orii et al, 2003). Kandikattu et al, created a new chronic EP-associated PC mouse model by giving mice a mixture of cerulean (50µg/kg body weight.) and azoxymethane (AOM) (10mg/kg b.wt.). Several pathogenic characteristics such as ADM, ductal cell differentiation, and PanIN were developed in CP mice induced with cerulean-AOM. Accumulating macrophages in the pancreas, trigger NLRP3 which induced IL-18, resulted in eosinophilic inflammation. It was found that, NLRP3-regulated, IL-18-induced eosinophil buildup and degranulation, merging pancreatic ducts, pancreatic intraepithelial neoplasia 1-3, and intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasm in cerulean-AOM induced mice model

The pathogenesis of pancreatic neoplasm via the afore mentioned pathways may be aided by NLRP3-regulated IL-18-induced eosinophilic inflammation, which has characteristics similar to human malignancy. Most importantly, it was shown that IL-18 neutralisation or deficiency in mice prevents

the development of most of the clinical features seen in PC, and that IL-18-induced pancreatic eosinophilia is linked to the promotion of CP-mediated PC phenotypic development. In a cerulein-with-AOM-induced inflammation-mediated murine model of PC, It was found that, both IL-18 gene deficiency and neutralised anti-IL-18 immunotherapy down-regulate profibrotic and oncogenic proteins and pathological features, such as inhibition of acinar cell hypertrophy, ADM, and proinflammatory stroma, including PanIN1, PanIN2, and PanIN3 formation (Kandikattu et al, 2021).

Future work and my thoughts

- ❖ My Future thoughts on this work are evaluation of chronic pancreatitis and pancreatic cancer model in cerulein treated GATA-1 knockout, IL-5 knockout mice as well as in Cerulein-AOM induced PC model or other AOM analogues may be used
- ❖ My thinking is that, we need to work more on the effect of different granules (components) of eosinophils in pancreatic eosinophilia. We also need to check Trypsin involvement in pancreatic eosinophilia.

References

Manohar, M., Kandikattu, H.K., Venkateshaiah, S.U., Yadavalli, C.S. and Mishra, A., 2021, March. Eosinophils in the pathogenesis of

pancreatic disorders. In **Seminars in Immunopathology** (pp. 1-12). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

Manohar, M., Verma, A.K., Venkateshaiah, S.U. and Mishra, A., 2018. Role of eosinophils in the initiation and progression of pancreatitis pathogenesis. **American Journal of Physiology-Gastrointestinal and Liver Physiology**, 314(2), pp.G211-G222.

Niranjan R, Mavi P, Rayapudi M, Dynda S, Mishra A. Pathogenic role of mast cells in experimental eosinophilic esophagitis. **Am J PhysiolGastrointest Liver Physiol**304: G1087–G1094, 2013. doi:10.1152/ajpgi.00070.2013.

Kandikattu, H.K., Manohar, M., Verma, A.K., Kumar, S., Yadavalli, C.S., Venkateshaiah, S.U. and Mishra, A., 2021. Macrophages-induced IL-18-mediated eosinophilia promotes characteristics of pancreatic malignancy. **Life science alliance**, 4(8).

Xue J, Sharma V, Hsieh MH, Chawla A, Murali R, Pandol SJ, Habtezion A. Alternatively activated macrophages promote pancreatic fibrosis in chronic pancreatitis. **Nat Commun** 6: 7158, 2015. doi:10.1038/ncomms8158.

Orii S, Yamaguchi T, Anzai H, Saito S, Chiba T, Suzuki K (2003) Chemoprevention for colorectal tumorigenesis associated with chronic colitis in mice via apoptosis. **J ExpClin Cancer Res** 22: 41–46.

Euscher E, Vaswani K, Frankel W (2000) Eosinophilic pancreatitis: A rare entity that can mimic a pancreatic neoplasm. **Ann DiagnPathol** 4: 379–385.